

Terpenoids. Part LXXII: A New Synthesis of Propylure

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3-(3-Carboxypropyl)-allyl vinyl ether, prepared from ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-heptenoate is transformed into 8-formyl-*trans*-5-octenoate through Claisen rearrangement. This aldehyde when submitted to Wittig reaction with 1-*n*-propyl-*n*-butyl-triphenylphosphonium iodide in DMSO affords ethyl-10-*n*-propyl-*trans*-5,9-tridecadienoate which on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride and subsequent reaction with acetic anhydride in pyridine furnishes propylure.

PROPYLURE, the acetate of an 18-carbon acyclic alcohol is a sex attractant produced in extremely small amount by the virgin female pink ball worm moth, *Pectinophora gossypiella*¹ and was identified as 10-propyl-*trans*-5,9-tridecadienyl acetate (I) through its spectral data.

This compound is believed to be the first reported natural constituent possessing an unusual *n*-propyl branching. With its unique structural features, coupled with the biological activity, propylure has attracted the attention of many workers. As a result, a number of syntheses of this compound have been reported²⁻⁶ since its isolation.

In the present communication, we report another convenient synthesis of propylure. The new approach is based on the fact that the intramolecular rearrangement of appropriate allyl vinyl ethers results in the formation of γ, δ -unsaturated aldehydes, in which the double bond has a *trans*-geometry^{7,8}. The sequence of reactions is given below :

Ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-heptenoate⁹ (II) was transformed into its vinyl ether (III) with ethyl vinyl ether, in the presence of a catalytic amount of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate⁸ in 45.2% yield. The allyl vinyl ether (III) was subjected to Claisen rearrangement⁸ in a sealed tube, in an atmosphere of nitrogen to produce ethyl-8-formyl-*trans*-5-octenoate in 60% yield after purification. The aldehyde (IV) when submitted to Wittig reaction with 1-*n*-propyl-*n*-butyl-triphenylphosphonium iodide² in DMSO afforded, after purification, the diene-ester(V) in 50% yield. The ester (V) was smoothly reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in dry ether to give the corresponding alcohol (VI in 75% yield). Finally, the carbinol (VI) was converted into its acetate (I) using

acetic anhydride in pyridine². The identity of the synthetic compound was established through the comparison of its IR spectrum with that of authentic sample.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer, model 337 Infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films.

3-(3-Carboxypropyl)-allyl vinyl ether (III) : Ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-heptenoate (II; 10 g), prepared by the known procedure⁹ was mixed with ethyl vinyl ether (100 ml) and freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (1.3 g) and the reaction mixture was heated under gentle reflux for 18 hr. The reaction mixture was chilled in ice, mixed with cold sodium carbonate solution (10%; 100 ml) and stirred for 30 min. The organic layer was separated and dried over anhy-

potassium carbonate. The evaporation of the solvent and chromatography of the residue over alumina with petroleum ether-benzene (10 : 1) gave the vinyl ether (III) which was subsequently distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 95°C/10 mm, yield 5.2 g (45.2%); η_D^{30} 1.4520. ν_{max} 3050, 1730, 1620, 1450, 1360, 1235, 1190, 1035, 1020, 910, 810 and 750 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 66.35; H, 9.50; calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$: C, 66.64; H, 9.15%).

Ethyl-8-formyl-trans-5-octenoate (IV) : The allyl vinyl ether (III; 5.0 g) was heated for 30 min. at 180°C in nitrogen atmosphere in a fully immersed sealed tube. Subsequent distillation under reduced pressure provide the aldehyde (IV; 3 g), yield 60%, b.p. 110°C/10 mm, η_D^{30} 1.4510. ν_{max} 2720, 1735–1730, 1640, 1455, 1370, 1235, 1030, 970 and 850 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 66.71; H, 9.42; calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$: C, 66.64; H, 9.15%).

Ethyl 10-n-propyl-trans-5,9-tridecadienoate (V) : A solution of methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (1 g) and dimethylsulphoxide (10 ml). This on treatment with 1-n-propyl-n-butyltriphenyl-phosphonium iodide (10.2 g)² in dimethylsulphoxide (22 ml) formed intense red coloured phosphorane. After stirring the phosphorane at room temp. for 30 min. the aldehyde (IV; 3.5 g) in THF (15 ml) was introduced slowly, keeping the temperature below 10°C. The contents were stirred for 2 hr., at room temp. and then left overnight. Thereafter, the contents were poured into ice-water and extracted thoroughly with petroleum ether (40°–60°C). Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was purified by column chromatography over alumina (benzene-petroleum ether, 10 : 1) and vacuum distillation to furnish the diene ester (V), yield 2.5 g (50%), b.p. 130°–135°C/5 mm., η_D^{30} 1.4562. ν_{max} 1730, 1655, 1455, 1365, 1235, 1030, 965, 850, 830 and 750 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 77.34; H, 11.67; Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.09; H, 11.50%).

1-Hydroxy-10-propyl-trans-5,9-tridecadiene (VI) : A solution of the ester (V; 2.4 g) in dry ether (25 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride in dry ether (100 ml). The contents were stirred for 4 hr at 50°C and then poured into ice cold solution of sodium sulphate.

The ether layer was separated, the aqueous phase extracted with ether and the combined extracts were washed with water. Evaporation of solvent and distillation of the residue gave the alcohol (VI) yield 1.5 g (75%); b.p. 140°–45°C/1 mm. η_D^{30} 1.4675. Lit.² η_D^{25} 1.4715. ν_{max} 3400, 1655, 1455, 1365, 1140, 1055, 965, 830 and 730 cm^{-1} , which are comparable to those reported in literature². (Found : C, 80.85; H, 12.45; calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$: C, 80.60; H, 12.68%).

1-Acetoxy-10-n-propyl-trans-5,9-tridecadiene (I) : A solution of the alcohol (VI; 1.4 g) in pyridine (1.4 g) and acetic anhydride (3.4 g) was kept for 48 hr at room temp. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, extracted with ether and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina (pet. ether 40°–60°C) and finally distilled under reduced pressure to afford (I); yield 1.1 g, (67.4%), b.p. 130–35°C/1 mm, η_D^{30} 1.4530, Lit.² η_D^{24} 1.4610. ν_{max} 1732, 1460, 1450, 1380, 1355, 1230, 1115, 1035, 965, 835 and 727 cm^{-1} which are exactly identical with those of the authentic sample. (Found : C, 77.43; H, 11.17; calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.09; H, 11.50%).

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